

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR THE COMPUTATION OF THRESHOLD CONDITIONS AND SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS FOR A LYMPHATIC *FILARIASIS* DISEASE MODEL

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ABSTRACT

An Ordinary Differential equation (ODE) model to study the transmission dynamics of lymphatic *filariasis* is proposed with 8 nonlinear mutually disjoint compartments. The model is proven to be mathematically and epidemiologically well posed. The basic reproduction number, R_0 , was computed using epidemiological approach. Sensitivity analysis was performed to find the impact of the model parameters on the basic reproduction number, R_0 . The public health implication of the result of the sensitivity analysis is presented.

Key words: Epidemiological Computation, Threshold Conditions, Sensitivity Analysis, Lymphatic *Filariasis*.

INTRODUCTION

Lymphatic *filariasis*, a neglected tropical disease, remain a major health and socioeconomic problem in many low-income countries. Lymphatic filariasis currently affects 120 million people worldwide (WHO, 2019). According to World Health Organisation (WHO, 2019), lymphatic filariasis is endemic in India, Indonesia and Nigeria.

There are more than 500 filarial parasites that are known to infect mammals, birds, reptiles and amphibians (Ukaga *et al.*, 2010). *Wuchereria bancrofti*, *Brugia malayi*, *Onchocerca volvulus*, *Loa Loa*, *Mansonella perstans*, *Mansonella strepocerca*, *Mansonella ozzardi* and *Brugia timori* are the common parasites of man. The adult of *Brugia malayi*, *Brugia timori* and *Wuchereria bancrofti* inhabit the lymphatic system, hence, the disease they cause is called lymphatic *filariasis* (Ukaga *et al.*, 2010). Lymphatic *filariasis* is caused by the thread-like parasitic worms called filariae. The worms have an estimated active reproductive span of 4-6 years, producing millions of small immature microfilariae, which circulates in the peripheral blood (WHO, 2019). They are transmitted from person to person by several species of mosquitoes (WHO, 2019). The symptoms of lymphatic filariasis vary from one

infected person to another. The symptoms of lymphatic filariasis, includes chills and fever, swellings in hands, testis and legs commonly called elephantiasis (WHO, 2019).

Mathematical modelling of infectious diseases has continue to be an area of active research. Over the years, mathematical models have been formulated to study the transmission dynamics of infectious diseases under various circumstances. Several mathematical models of lymphatic filariasis and other vector-borne diseases abound in literature (Iyare *et al.*, 2014; Nwamtobe *et al.*, 2017); Iddi *et al.*, 2016a & b; Yan Cheng Iddi *et al.*, 2017; Bhunu and Mushayabasa, 2012; Jambulingam Iddi *et al.*, 2015). In all the models considered, the basic reproduction number R_0 , was computed using the next generation matrix by Van de Driessche and Watmough (2002). In this work, we proposed a new model to study the transmission dynamics of lymphatic filariasis. The basic reproduction number was computed using the epidemiological approach instead of the next generation approach.

METHODS

The pathogenesis of lymphatic *filariasis*, signs and symptoms and diagnosis as well as current epidemiological data were presented. Thereafter, an extensive review of lymphatic filariasis were carried out. Mathematical tools and techniques employed in the development and analysis of the formulated model were identified and studied. These methods and techniques include; positivity of solutions of the model and other methods used for the study of dynamical systems. Based on the biology and natural history of lymphatic *filariasis*, we formulated novel deterministic mathematical model. The model was rigorously analyzed. The following system of 8 nonlinear ordinary differential equations were formulated. The model is given below.

The total human population at time t , denoted by $N_h(t)$, is subdivided into five mutually-disjoint compartments of susceptible humans $S_h(t)$, latent individual $E_h(t)$, Asymptomatic individual $I_A(t)$, Symptomatic individual $I_S(t)$, and Treated individual $T_h(t)$. The total vector population at

time t , denoted by $N_m(t)$ is subdivided into three mutually-disjoint compartments of susceptible mosquitoes $S_m(t)$, latent mosquitoes $E_m(t)$ and infectious mosquitoes $I_m(t)$, so that

$$N_h(t) = S_h(t) + E_h(t) + I_A(t) + I_S(t) + T_h(t) \quad (1)$$

and

$$N_m(t) = S_m(t) + E_m(t) + I_m(t) \quad (2)$$

Based on the assumptions above, the model is given by the following system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dS_h}{dt} &= \psi_h - \lambda_m S_h - \mu_h S_h \\ \frac{dE_h}{dt} &= \lambda_m S_h + \omega \lambda_m T_h - (\alpha_1 + \mu_h) E_h \\ \frac{dI_A}{dt} &= \alpha_1 E_h - (\alpha_2 + \mu_h) I_A \\ \frac{dI_S}{dt} &= \alpha_2 I_A - (\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h) I_S \\ \frac{dT_h}{dt} &= \eta_h I_S - \omega \lambda_m T_h - \mu_h T_h \\ \frac{dS_m}{dt} &= \psi_m - \lambda_h S_m - \mu_m S_m \\ \frac{dE_m}{dt} &= \lambda_h S_m - \alpha_m E_m - \mu_m E_m \\ \frac{dI_m}{dt} &= \alpha_m E_m - \mu_m I_m \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where

$$\lambda_m = \frac{\beta_m \sigma_m \sigma_h I_m}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \quad (4)$$

And

$$\lambda_h = \frac{\beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h (\eta_1 E_h + \eta_2 I_A + I_S)}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \quad (5)$$

Table 1: Description of variables of the model

Variable	Description
$S_h(t)$	Population of susceptible humans
$E_h(t)$	Population of humans with latent lymphatic filariasis
$I_A(t)$	Population of humans with asymptomatic lymphatic filariasis
$I_S(t)$	Population of humans with symptomatic lymphatic filariasis
$T_h(t)$	Population of humans treated of lymphatic filariasis
$S_m(t)$	Population of susceptible mosquitoes
$E_m(t)$	Population of latent mosquitoes
$I_m(t)$	Population of infectious mosquitoes

Table 2: Description o parameters of the model

PARAMETER	DESCRIPTION
μ_h, μ_m	Natural death rates for humans and mosquitoes
ψ_h, ψ_m	Recruitment rates for humans and mosquitoes
β_m	Transmission probability from mosquito to humans
β_h	Transmission probability from human to mosquitoes
σ_m	Number of times a mosquito bites humans per unit time
σ_h	Maximum number of mosquito bites a human can receive per unit time
α_1, α_2	Progression rates for lymphatic filariasis
ω	Reinfection rates for lymphatic after treatment
η_h	Treatment rates for lymphatic filariasis
η_1, η_2	Reduced transmissibility of lymphatic filariasis by latent and asymptomatic Humans in comparison to symptomatic humans

δ_h

Disease-induced death rates for individuals with lymphatic filariasis.

Basic Properties of Model (3)

Theorem 1: Let the initial conditions for the model (3) be given as $S_h(o) > 0, E_h(o) > 0, I_A(o) > 0, I_S(o) > 0, T_h(o) > 0, S_m(o) > 0, E_m(o) > 0, I_m(o) > 0$. Then the orbits $(S_h(t), E_h(t), I_A(t), I_S(t), T_h(t), S_m(t), E_m(t), I_m(t))$ of the model with positive initial conditions, will remain positive for all time t.

Proof:

Consider the first equation of model (3)

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} = \psi_h - \lambda_m S_h - \mu_h S_h$$

(6)

Without loss of generality, we can write equation (6) as

$$\frac{dS_h}{dt} \geq -(\lambda_m + \mu_h) S_h$$

$$\frac{dS_h}{S_h} \geq -(\lambda_m + \mu_h) dt \tag{7}$$

Integrating (7) with respect to t in $[0, t_1]$ gives

$$S_h(t_1) \geq S_h(0) \exp\left\{-\int_0^{t_1} (\lambda_m + \mu_h) dt\right\} > 0, \forall t > 0$$

Hence

$$S_h(t) > 0, \forall t > 0$$

Using similar approach, it can be shown that the other state variables of model (3) will remain positive for all time $t > 0$.

Theorem 2: Let $(S_h(t), E_h(t), I_A(t), I_S(t), T_h(t), S_m(t), E_m(t), I_m(t))$ be trajectories of model (3)

with initial conditions and the biological feasible region given by the set $D = D_h \times D_m$

Where $D_h = \{(S_h(t), E_h(t), I_A(t), I_S(t), T_h(t)) \in R_+^5 : N_h(t) \leq \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}\}$ and

$D_m = \{(S_m(t), E_m(t), I_m(t)) \in R_+^3 : N_m \leq \frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m}\}$ is positively-invariant and attracts all the positive trajectories of model (3).

Proof:

The rate of change of the total human population $N_h(t)$ described by model (3) is given as

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} = \psi_h - \mu_h N_h - \delta_h I_S \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is obtained by adding the first five equations on the right hand side of model (3).

Without loss of generality, we can write equation (8) as

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} \leq \psi_h - \mu_h N_h \quad (9)$$

Using integrating factor given as $e^{\mu_h t}$, we have

$$\frac{dN_h}{dt} e^{\mu_h t} + \mu_h N_h e^{\mu_h t} \leq \psi_h e^{\mu_h t} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) can be rewritten as

$$\int_0^t \frac{dN_h}{dt} (N_h e^{\mu_h t}) dt \leq \psi_h \int_0^t e^{\mu_h t} dt \quad (11)$$

These implies that

$$N_h(t) e^{\mu_h t} - N_h(0) \leq \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h} (e^{\mu_h t} - 1) \quad (12)$$

Finally, solving for $N_h(t)$ from equation (12) gives

$$N_h(t) \leq N_h(0) e^{-\mu_h t} + \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h} (e^{\mu_h t} - 1) \quad (13)$$

In particular, if $N_h(0) \leq \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}$, then $N_h(t) \leq \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}$ for all $t > 0$

Similarly, it can be shown for the total mosquito population.

That if $N_m(0) \leq \frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m}$, then $N_m(t) \leq \frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m}$, for all $t > 0$.

Hence, the set D is positively invariant.

Moreover, if $N_h(0) > \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}$, and $N_m(0) > \frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m}$, then either the orbits enters the domain D in finite

time or $N_h(t)$ asymptotically approaches $\frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ and $N_m(t)$ asymptotically approaches

$$\frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m} \text{ as } t \rightarrow \infty.$$

Thus, the domain D attracts all the trajectories in R_+^8 .

Since the domain D is positively invariant, it is enough to study the dynamics of the flow generated by model (3) in D.

We conclude that model (3) is both mathematically and epidemiologically well posed.

Epidemiological Computation of Basic Reproduction Number

The basic reproduction number R_0 for lymphatic *filariasis* is the average number of secondary cases that one infectious individual (or mosquito) would generate over the duration of the infectious period if introduced into a susceptible human (or mosquito) population.

Susceptible humans S_h acquire lymphatic *filariasis* infection following effective contact with an infected mosquito I_m . The number of human infection generated by an infected mosquito is the product of the infection rate of infected mosquitoes, the probability that an exposed mosquito survives the exposed stage and moves to the infectious stage, and the average life expectancy of the infected mosquito.

The average number of new human infection is given as

$$\frac{\beta_m \sigma_m \sigma_h S_h}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \cdot \frac{\alpha_m}{\alpha_m + \mu_m} \cdot \frac{1}{\mu_m} \quad (14)$$

At the disease-free equilibrium: $N_h^* = S_h^* = \frac{\psi_h}{\mu_h}$ and $N_m^* = S_m^* = \frac{\psi_m}{\mu_m}$ (15)

Substituting equation (15) into equation (14) and simplifying, we have

$$\frac{\beta_m \sigma_m \sigma_h \alpha_m \psi_h}{(\alpha_m + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) represent the total number of secondary lymphatic *filariasis* infection in human caused by one infected mosquito.

Similarly, susceptible mosquito S_m acquire lymphatic *filariasis* parasite infection following effective contact with an exposed human E_h , asymptomatic human I_A and symptomatic human I_S .

The number of mosquito infections generated by an exposed human E_h is

$$\frac{\eta_1 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h S_m}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha_1 + \mu_h} \quad (17)$$

That is infection rate of exposed human multiplied by the average duration in the exposed class.

Using equation (15), equation (17) becomes

$$\frac{\eta_1 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (18)$$

The number of mosquito infection generated by an asymptomatic human I_A , is the product of the infection rate of asymptomatic humans, the probability that an exposed human survives the exposed stage and move to the asymptomatic stage and the average duration in the asymptomatic class.

The number of mosquito infection generated by the asymptomatic class is

$$\frac{\eta_2 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h S_m}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \cdot \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_1 + \mu_h} \cdot \frac{1}{\alpha_2 + \mu_h} \quad (19)$$

Substituting equation (15) into equation (19) and simplifying, we have

$$\frac{\eta_2 \alpha_1 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (20)$$

Finally, the number of mosquito infections generated by symptomatic humans I_S is given by the product of the infection rate of symptomatic humans, the probability that asymptomatic humans survive the asymptomatic stage and move to the symptomatic class and the average duration in the symptomatic class.

Thus, the average number of mosquito infection generated by the symptomatic humans is given by

$$\frac{\beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h S_m}{\sigma_m N_m + \sigma_h N_h} \cdot \frac{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_h)(\alpha_2 + \mu_h)} \cdot \frac{1}{(\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h)} \quad (21)$$

Substituting equation (15) into equation (21) and simplifying, we have

$$\frac{\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (22)$$

The average number of new mosquito infections generated by infected humans (exposed, asymptomatic and symptomatic) is given by the addition of equations (18, 20, 22)

That is

$$\frac{\eta_1 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} + \frac{\eta_2 \alpha_1 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} + \frac{\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (23)$$

Simplifying we have

$$\frac{\beta_h \sigma_m \sigma_h \psi_m \mu_h (\eta_1 g_2 g_3 + \alpha_1 \eta_2 g_3 + \alpha_1 \alpha_2)}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)} \quad (24)$$

Equation (24) represent the total number of lymphatic *filariasis* infected mosquitoes caused by (exposed, asymptomatic and symptomatic) humans.

The geometric mean of equations (16) and (24) give the threshold conditions for disease eradication.

It is also known as the basic reproduction number R_0

The geometric mean of equation (16) and (24) is

$$R_0 = \sqrt{\frac{\beta_m \beta_h \sigma_m^2 \sigma_h^2 \psi_m \psi_h \alpha_m \mu_h (\eta_1 g_2 g_3 + \alpha_1 \eta_2 g_3 + \alpha_1 \alpha_2)}{(\alpha_1 + \mu_m)(\alpha_2 + \mu_m)(\eta_h + \delta_h + \mu_h)(\alpha_m + \mu_m)(\sigma_m \psi_m \mu_h + \sigma_h \psi_h \mu_m)}} \quad (25)$$

Sensitivity Analysis

Here, we assess the impact of the parameters of the model on the basic reproduction number R_0 , by computing the elasticity index using sensitivity analysis.

Sensitivity analysis is commonly used to determine the robustness of model predictions on parameter values. It is used to discover parameters that have a higher impact on the basic reproduction number. It allow us to measure the relative change in a state variable when a parameter changes. According to (Chitnis et al.,(2008); Moore et al.,(2012); Ngonghala et al.,(2014)), the normalize forward sensitivity index of a variable to a parameter is the ratio of the relative change in the variable to the relative change in the parameter.

The analysis carried out in this section, is based on the parameter values shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Parameter values

Parameters	Baseline values	Reference
μ_h	0.02041 year ⁻¹	World Bank (2018)
μ_m	0.0714 year ⁻¹	World Bank (2018)
ψ_h	3768410 year ⁻¹	Country meter (2015)
ψ_m	10000 year ⁻¹	Country meter (2015)
β_m	variable year ⁻¹	WHO, (2019)
β_h	variable year ⁻¹	WHO, (2019)
σ_m	620.39 year ⁻¹	Hussaini <i>et al.</i> (2016)
σ_h	1168 year ⁻¹	Hussaini <i>et al.</i> (2016)
α_1	0.15 year ⁻¹	Assumed
α_2	0.15 year ⁻¹	Assumed
ω	0.0001 year ⁻¹	Assumed
η_h	0.65 year ⁻¹	Hussaini <i>et al.</i> (2016)
η_1	0.3 year ⁻¹	Okosun and Makinde (2014)
η_2	0.3 year ⁻¹	Okosun and Makinde (2014)
δ_h	0.0001 year ⁻¹	Okosun and Makinde (2014)

The elasticity indices of the basic reproduction number are presented in the table below in order of decreasing magnitude.

Table 4: Elasticity Index

Parameters	Elasticity index
μ_m	-1.45788
σ_m	+0.990603
β_m	+0.5
β_h	+0.5
ψ_m	+0.490603
ψ_h	+0.490603
α_m	+0.467277
α_2	-0.44009
μ_h	+0.367504
η_h	-0.244939
α_1	+0.0598564
σ_h	+0.00939691
δ_h	-0.0000163293

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4 provides the elasticity indices of R_0 , to the model parameters. The sign before the value indicate whether to increase the value of the parameter or reduce it, in order to bring down the value of the basic reproduction number to less than one. A negative sign means that the value of the parameter should be increased while a positive sign means that the value of the parameter should be reduced.

Looking at the elasticity indices in Table 4, the basic reproduction number is most sensitive to the death rate for mosquitoes, μ_m , with an elasticity index of -1.45788. What this mean is that if the death rate for mosquitoes is reduced by 1%, the basic reproduction number, R_0 , will decrease by approximately 1.46%. The basic reproduction number is also sensitive to the following parameters; The number of times a mosquito bite humans, σ_m , with an elasticity index of +0.990603, probability of transmission of lymphatic filariasis from mosquitoes to humans, β_m , with an elasticity index of +0.5, probability of transmission of lymphatic filariasis from human to mosquitoes, β_h , with an elasticity index of +0.5, recruitment rate for mosquitoes, ψ_m , with elasticity index of +0.490603,

treatment rate, η_h , with elasticity index of -0.244939 etc. The basic reproduction number is least sensitive to the disease-induced death rate for humans, δ_h , with an elasticity index of -0.0000163293.

CONCLUSION

We proposed and analysed 8 nonlinear ordinary differential equations models to study the transmission dynamics of lymphatic *filariasis*. The model was shown to be mathematically and epidemiologically well posed. The basic reproduction number was computed using the epidemiological approach. Sensitivity analysis was carried out to find the impact of the model parameters on the basic reproduction number. The public health implications of the results in the sensitivity analysis is that increasing the death rate of mosquitoes, reducing the number of times a mosquito bite humans (through the use of windows and doors screens), reducing the rate of transmission of lymphatic *filariasis* from mosquito to humans, reducing the rate of lymphatic *filariasis* transmission from human to mosquitoes, reducing the recruitment rate for mosquitoes (by destroying mosquitoes breeding sites), increasing the treatment rate for persons with lymphatic filariasis infection, will bring down the basic reproduction number to less than one. This means that the disease can be eradicated.

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